

Sonia-Doris Andraş*

**CRAFTING ILLUSIONS:
FASHION AS A MEANS OF DECODING SOCIAL AND
CULTURAL HISTORY IN INTERWAR BUCHAREST**

***Abstract:** This paper proposes an overview of the intertwined streams of cultural, political, economic and social aspects that made up the fashion-consuming women's interwar Bucharest, through the scope of fashion studies. For this, I will outline the extended methodological and conceptual scope which defines fashion studies in correlation with historical analysis. This wide range of research includes cultural anthropology, semiotics, sociology, cultural, gender and identity studies, adding to the technical, artistic, and philosophical implications already popular in pursuits of costume history. My paper will be centred around the idea of crafting illusions. I will use the word "craft" both in its magical and metaphysical sense, as in "witchcraft", but also suggesting all aspects of craftsmanship. Therefore, my study deals with the conception, production, dissemination, consumption, and interpretation of fashionability. Drawing from this double-meaning, crafting illusions means invoking an idealised reality of prosperity, success, and power, which can hide a less glamorous reality. It can also be weaponised, from social control to building a national image.*

I will thus use the methods of fashion studies to interpret how the elegant Bucharester myth was constructed in an era of great upheavals. I aim to illustrate the fashion studies methodological and conceptual frameworks as a valid method of research, which has already been recognised as such in Western academia as a full-fledged discipline blending media, design, humanities, science, marketing, and politics. I will juxtapose the images seen in fashionable touristic spaces, such as Calea Victoriei, to the grim realities of a world recovering from past

* PhD Candidate (Thesis approved for VIVA in 2020), London College of Fashion, University of the Arts London.

trauma, soon to delve into a new disaster. This will allow a snapshot of interwar Romania's complexity through the lens of fashion.

Keywords: *fashion, interwar Bucharest, women, consumerism, myth, elegance.*

This paper aims to illustrate the wide scope of fashion studies, beyond the realms of costume history and sociology. I will outline the theoretical evolution of late-twentieth-century fashion theory until today conceptually and methodologically, until it was acknowledged as a genuine academic field, particularly in the West. I will also show how scholars from other fields tangentially dealing with fashion subjects progressed in the past decades into fully-fledged fashion theorists within specialised University departments. As a branch of cultural studies, fashion studies employ an interdisciplinary methodology and the themes can include the traditional artistic, historical and sociological aspects, but they mostly delve into gender or urban studies, semiotics, economy, science, medicine, anthropology, psychology, politics or industry-based subjects. Consequently, fashion studies are a generous field of research for both practice-based and theory-based academics, ranging from mainstream to marginal areas of interest. This is especially useful for spaces, like Romania, where this type of approach has been little used. I will therefore use examples from interwar Bucharest women's lives to demonstrate the adaptability and connectivity allowed through an innately multi-dimensional analysis. I will differentiate the theoretical evolution of fashion theory with I termed "craft of illusion", from the conceptual and philosophical approaches to the subject, the "illusion of craft". This is a wordplay on the idea that charm or glamour have evolved from connotations of witchcraft. Similarly, the word "craft" can signify both technical prowess and spell casting. As the fashion system is inherently based on illusion, on an eternal present that becomes past as soon as it is verbalised, I connected it to the idea of craft.

The Craft of Illusion

Writings dealing with fashion and dress beyond illustrated costume histories, begin with the nineteenth century. Perspectives

habitually took a philosophical, moralising route, which can explain the intense division between proponents and detractors until recently¹. Advocates for women's larger participation in public life vehemently opposed fashion and those who adhered by its fleeting rules. Specialised literature maintained a steady bias towards artistic or conceptual approaches, while its otherwise-assumed commercial aspect still largely ignored functioning as a "tacit hypothesis"², essentially bringing new or marginal items into the mainstream³, thus offering a platform for peripheral individuals, ideas and customs⁴. For Eastern Europe, its accessibility mirrored its pre-modern elites-masses differentiations, until new practices were readily adopted by those who wished to be 'modern', Western-like, and urban. In Greater Romania, this modernisation also applied to fashionable modifications to the national costumes, where contemporary styles blend with traditional motifs⁵.

The so-called "fashion classics"⁶ reflect the sociological and philosophical inquest throughout the nineteenth and most of the twentieth centuries. Historian, mathematician, writer and philosopher Thomas Carlyle is one of the most famous, with his philosophical 1836 novel *Sartor Resartus*. In the second half of the nineteenth century, biologist, anthropologist and sociologist Herbert Spencer presented his "sartorial Protestantism" and evolutionary perspective. Economist and sociologist Thorstein Veblen's economic and sociological investigation delved into the leisure class in 1899. Sociologist Georg Simmel

¹ Yuniya Kawamura, *Fashion-ology: An Introduction to Fashion Studies*, Oxford and New York, Berg, 2005, pp. 6-7.

² Monica Titton, "Fashion Criticism Unraveled: A Sociological Critique of Criticism in Fashion Media", in *International Journal of Fashion Studies*, vol. 3, January 2016, p. 211.

³ Paula von Wachenfeldt, "The Myth of Luxury in a Fashion World", in *Fashion, Style & Popular Culture*, vol. 5, October 2018, p. 314.

⁴ Rebecca Arnold, *Fashion, Desire, and Anxiety: Image and Morality in the 20th Century*, New Brunswick NJ, Rutgers University Press, 2001, p. 4.

⁵ Djurdja Bartlett, "Introduction to Dress and Fashion in East Europe, Russia, and the Caucasus", in Djurdja Bartlett, Pamela Smith (eds), *Berg Encyclopedia of World Dress and Fashion*, Oxford, Berg, 2010, p. 6.

⁶ See Michael Carter, *Fashion Classics from Carlyle to Barthes*, Oxford and New York, Berg Publishers, 2003.

represented the late nineteenth and early twentieth century with a neo-Kantian perspective. Experimental psychologist and psychoanalyst John Carl Flügel filtered his early twentieth-century experience through experimental psychology and psychoanalysis. Author, art critic and historian James Laver used his expertise as a museum curator and art historian in tracing costume history throughout the twentieth century, until the mid-1970s. Fashion as a contemporary research subject reflects its visible practices, leading towards a purported “blurring of genres”, which occurred when academics from different specialities began migrating in its direction⁷. It extends beyond the so-called meta-theoretical attempts to answer ‘why’- questions⁸, to increasingly interdisciplinary, albeit more focused, studies on all aspects of the phenomenon. While the scholars themselves may be specialised in a particular field, fashion inquiry will always require a panoramic understanding. The narrower the focus, the higher the need for a proper methodological approach⁹.

In 1966, semiotician Roland Barthes described fashion as a paradoxical mechanism functioning on “the imitation that which has first shown itself as inimitable”. For this, he continued, it becomes a sociological interest as it illustrates patterns of social and cultural change, divorced from the traditional “stagnant nature of society” where dress is immutably coded and hierarchized¹⁰. Moreover, sociologist Joanne Entwistle contended that in ignoring the close connection between clothing and the body, leading to classical social theory’s failure to recognise the significance of dress¹¹. This link between modernity and its discontinuities has been further examined by sociologist Anthony

⁷ Heike Jense, “Locating Fashion/Studies: Research Methods, Sites and Practices”, in Heike Jense (ed), *Fashion Studies: Research Methods, Sites and Practices*, London, Bloomsbury, 2016, pp. 2-3.

⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 5.

⁹ Agnès Rocamora and Anneke Smelik, “Thinking Through Fashion: An Introduction”, in Agnès Rocamora, Anneke Smelik (eds), *Thinking Through Fashion: A Guide to Key Theorists*, London and New York, I.B. Tauris, 2015, p. 3.

¹⁰ Roland Barthes, *The Language of Fashion*, Andy Stafford, Michael Carter (eds), Andy Stafford (tran), Oxford and New York, Berg, 2006, p. 91.

¹¹ Joanne Entwistle, “The Dressed Body”, in Linda Welters, Abby Lillethun (eds), *The Fashion Reader*, Oxford, Berg, 2014, p. 139.